

Family Institution and the Problems of Marriage in Contemporary Indian Society

Dr. Mahesh Krishna Mali

Associate Professor, Department of English,

BV's Matoshri Bayabai Shripatrao Kadam Mahavidyalaya, Kadegaon

Corresponding Author – Dr. Mahesh Krishna Mali

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Abstract:

The family and marriage system in today's Indian society is going through many changes. These changes are mainly due to the urbanization, globalization and new technology. Important issues include the shift from joint families to nuclear families, increase in divorce rates, gender inequality and financial stress that affects married life. The present study uses secondary data such as national surveys and recent research. It shows that traditional arranged marriages are slowly being replaced by love marriages and live-in-relationships. These new forms of relationships often face social criticism, problems of commitment and mental stress. The findings show that unemployment among young men delays their marriages. Women face more pressure in marriage and household responsibilities because of patriarchal thinking and practices like dowry. Dating apps sometimes lead to shallow relationships and cheating, which reduces trust between people. Live-in-relationships challenge traditional cultural values and can cause problems such as neglect of elders and weakening respect for parents. Although people in cities now enjoy more personal freedom and equality, these changes have also reduced the quality of family relationships and support systems. The paper concludes that modernization gives people more freedom, but it also creates new problems. Therefore, government policies are needed to improve mental health support, promote gender equality and reduce economic inequality. These steps are necessary to protect and strengthen the family institution in India's diverse society. This research paper studies how family and marriage are changing and what problems people are facing today.

Key Words: Marriage Transformation, Nuclear family, Gender inequality, Marriage patterns.

Introduction:

The family has always been the most important social institution in Indian society. It has given emotional, financial and social support to people for many generations. In traditional Hindu, Muslim and other cultural systems, the joint family was common. Many generations lived together under the authority of the father or elder male in this system. It promoted values like togetherness, respect for elders and stable marriages through arranged marriages. Marriage was not only a bond between two individuals but a sacred relationship between two families. It helped continue religion, caste traditions and

economic cooperation. However, rapid urbanization, globalization and the spread of digital technology changed these traditions. Today, Indian society witnessed drastic change in how people choose partners, form families and think about marriage. Young people are influenced by Western ideas through social media and education. Now they are giving more importance to personal choice, career goals and emotional happiness rather than family duty. This has led to late marriages, an increase in nuclear families and the belief that marriage is not always necessary for everyone.

These changes have caused more problems in marriage. In big cities, more women are filing for divorce because of incompatibility, cheating or domestic violence. Patriarchal practices like dowry still continue and increase family conflict and violence. Live-in-relationships challenge traditional cultural values and create issues about legal rights and social acceptance. Unemployment among educated young men delays marriage and creates stress. At the same time, women's financial independence helps them leave unhappy marriages, but it also brings social criticism.

This research paper studies these changes from a sociological point of view. Its main aims are to record changes in family and marriage patterns using data, to identify major problems such as instability, violence and weak family support systems and to suggest policies to make families stronger. This study is important because India has a large young population. Strong and stable families are necessary for national development. The paper shows that modernization gives freedom to individuals but also weakens family bonds.

Literature Review:

Scholars explain that Indian families have slowly changed from large joint families to smaller nuclear families because of industrialization, urbanization and globalization. In the past, joint families were based on sharing responsibilities and elders had strong authority. Marriages were arranged to maintain family status and traditions. Women were often treated as dependent members and the dowry system made their position weaker. After the 1990s economic reforms, many people moved to cities or abroad for jobs and families became smaller. Modern technology like mobile phones and video calls keeps families connected but it has also increased the gap between generations and made

many elderly people feel lonely. More women now work outside the home which supports equality in decision making, but it also creates tension with traditional family roles.

Marriage patterns are also changing. Studies by Pew Research Center show that most marriages are still arranged but young people increasingly prefer love marriages, especially in cities and inter caste marriages are slowly rising. Live-in-relationships, once considered unacceptable are now legally recognized through Supreme Court decisions under the Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act. People are marrying later because of education and jobs and child marriage has declined. Divorce rates are still low compared to other countries, but they are rising in urban areas with women filing most cases due to cruelty or incompatibility. Dowry and domestic violence remain serious problems as reported by National Crime Records Bureau. Technology has a mixed impact: dating apps give more freedom of choice but also increase fraud and emotional stress. Overall, modern Indian families face both progress and problems showing the need for further research and social support.

Research Methodology:

This study uses a qualitative secondary data analysis method by combining information from different reliable sources to give a clear and broad understanding of Indian family and marriage trends. The main data come from National Family Health Survey 5 conducted by International Institute for Population Sciences and ICF which provides national data on family structure, marriage, age at marriage and violence based on a very large sample of households, women and men. Crime related data on dowry and related offences were taken from National Crime Records Bureau. Additional information was collected from Pew Research Center, youth attitude surveys such as Gleeden Ipsos and recent

academic studies on globalization and marriage. The analysis compared trends from NFHS-3 to NFHS-5 to understand changes over time and differences between urban and rural areas and between men and women. Findings were grouped into themes like family structure, changing marriage patterns, violence and new social issues. The study mainly depends on self-reported data, which may underreport sensitive issues like divorce and violence and NFHS-5 data is slightly old so newer NCRB data were added. Since all data are publicly available, no ethical risk is involved and this desk based method allows a careful and wide social interpretation without fieldwork.

Findings and Discussion:

Data from the National Family Health Survey 5 shows that most Indian households are now nuclear families, meaning parents live only with their unmarried children. About 58% of families are nuclear and this number is higher in cities than in villages. The average family size has become smaller. Joint and extended families still exist, especially in rural areas where farming needs shared work and support. Because of globalization and job migration, many young people move away from their hometowns, which breaks joint families and leaves elderly parents feeling lonely. Nuclear families give more privacy and independence but they also reduce family support, increasing stress among youth and making old people more vulnerable.

Arranged marriages are still common but love marriages are slowly increasing among young people because of higher education and exposure to modern ideas. People now marry at a later age than before and child marriage has declined, though it still exists. Inter caste and inter religious marriages remain rare. Dating apps have made it easier for young people to choose partners but they also bring risks like fake

identities and unrealistic expectations. Live-in-relationships are becoming more accepted and are protected by courts but they challenge traditional ideas about marriage and family responsibility.

Divorce rates in India are still low compared to other countries but they are rising quickly in big cities like Delhi, Mumbai and Bengaluru. In some places, the number of divorce cases has doubled or tripled in the last ten years. Women now file most divorce cases in urban areas because they are more educated and financially independent. Common reasons for divorce include lack of understanding, extra-marital relationships, domestic violence and conflicts between career and family life. In rural areas, divorce is still rare because of social stigma and women's dependence on their husbands.

Dowry and domestic violence continue to be serious problems despite strict laws. According to the National Crime Records Bureau, thousands of dowry related cases and deaths are reported every year. About one third of married women have faced physical or sexual violence from their husbands, especially in poorer and less educated families and even in nuclear households. Dowry demands increase harassment of women and are linked to the preference for sons. Many young people still believe wife beating is justified which keeps this cycle of violence alive.

Technology has changed relationships in both good and bad ways. Dating apps give more freedom to choose partners but also increase cheating, fraud and emotional stress. Live-in-relationships face legal and social problems related to children and property. Mental health issues are rising: divorced people suffer from depression, elderly parents feel neglected in nuclear families and young people fear long term commitment because of job insecurity. While education and urban life bring freedom and equality, they also weaken the strong family support system that once protected Indian society.

Overall, modernization has given people more choices but has also broken many traditional bonds of care and responsibility.

Conclusions:

Contemporary family and marriage in India show a mix of tradition and modern change. Many families are now nuclear and people are choosing their partners and marrying later in life. Divorce and separation are still low but slowly increasing, which shows that individual freedom is becoming more important. At the same time, problems like dowry violence and weak family support systems show that true equality has not yet been achieved. Globalization has given people more independence, but it has also made many feel lonely and disconnected. Therefore, Indian society needs to adjust to these changes in a balanced way.

Several recommendations can help strengthen family and marriage institutions. First, government policies should strictly enforce laws against dowry and misuse of prenatal sex determination. Mental health services should be included in family courts and tax benefits should be given to families who take care of elderly members. These steps can reduce stress and protect vulnerable groups. Second, legal reforms are needed. Live in relationships should be given clear legal recognition across the country. Mutual consent divorces should be handled faster, along with proper counseling to help couples make informed decisions. This will reduce conflict and emotional suffering.

Third, education must play an important role. Schools should teach students about healthy

relationships, mutual respect, consent and basic financial skills. Awareness programs should also be conducted on safe dating practices and responsible use of digital platforms. Another important recommendation is economic measures are necessary. Skill development programs should be expanded to reduce youth unemployment. Laws related to property and inheritance should be gender neutral so that men and women are treated equally. Finally, more research is required. Long term studies should be done on live in relationships and the effects of digital technology on family life.

Thus, by promoting fair and flexible family systems, India can use its young population for inclusive development. The family institution still survives not in the same old form, but in a new and changing shape.

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